

Bridging the gap - from improvisation to innovation. Toward a specialised curriculum for hospital school educators

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ABSTRACT

Hospital schooling plays a critical role in ensuring educational continuity for chronically ill students. However, the field remains largely informal in Germany, Austria, and Switzerland, with significant gaps in systematic teacher training and professional support. This trina-tional study used an online-based needs assessment to evaluate current practices and identify core areas for professional develop-ment. Findings reveal high teacher commitment but substantial deficits in medical knowledge, specialised pedagogy, and institu-tional support structures. The study underscores the urgent need for standardised, interdisciplinary curricula and proposes actionable strategies for educational policy and practice. These findings con-tribute significantly to the international discourse on professionali-sation of educators in health contexts.

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Introduction

The education and psychosocial support of children and adolescents with chronic illnesses pose significant challenges for modern education systems. In Germany, Austria, and Switzerland, an estimated 12–16% of children and adolescents are affected by long-term health impairments (Dratva et al. 2020; Neuhauser and Poethko-Müller 2014). The report of the Swiss Health Observatory (Dratva et al. 2020) highlights the broad spectrum of these conditions, which often entail not only physical limitations but also psychological distress and social exclusion. Furthermore, the report underscores the necessity of cross-sector collaboration between education, healthcare, and social services. The educational sector, in particular, is crucial in providing psychosocial support to affected children. Initiatives such as school health services, multi-professional teams, and specially trained teachers could enhance educational opportunities and foster social inclusion. In this context, hospital schools and similar specialised educational institutions are gaining increas-ing importance, as they enable children with illnesses to continue their education

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seamlessly and facilitate their eventual reintegration into the regular school system. Findings from international contexts underscore this significance: A Finnish study by Äärelä, Määttä, and Uusiautti (2018) illustrates the complexity of collaboration between hospital school teachers and parents, which is crucial for ensuring pedagogical continuity and emotional support throughout hospitalisation and reintegration.

Recent German School Barometer (Robert 2024) findings emphasise the immense strain teachers face when dealing with heterogeneous classrooms. More than half of the surveyed teachers report being overwhelmed by the diversity of students' learning needs, and 71% experience this heterogeneity as a significant burden in their daily work. At the same time, many schools lack structured support systems and specialised offerings for students with psychosocial difficulties, which are often rated only 'satisfactory to poor'. These findings underscore the urgent need for professional support and targeted qualification programmes – particularly in settings such as hospital schools, where medical, emotional, and educational dimensions must be addressed in tandem. Todis, McCart, and Glang (2018) further emphasise that even in systems where hospital-to-school transition services exist, their provision is often inconsistent and educators frequently lack the knowledge to implement hospital recommendations effectively. This underlines the necessity for structured qualifications in interdisciplinary communication and individualised transition planning.

The WHO (2023) also emphasises the importance of health-promoting school measures, particularly for vulnerable groups such as children and adolescents with chronic illnesses. While the right to education for these students is legally enshrined, in practice, the question arises as to how this right can be effectively implemented in a manner that accommodates both their health needs and educational requirements (Haegeler and Hodge 2016). Despite decades of discussions on the professionalisation of teachers in this field, there is still no officially recognised or standardised curriculum for hospital school educators in Germany, Austria, or Switzerland. This gap results in insufficient systematic qualification of teachers and complicates the development of coherent and effective educational programmes for affected students. Given the particular challenges arising from the heterogeneity of illnesses, organisational frameworks, and multiprofessional demands, specific qualifications for teachers in this area are essential (Neuhauser and Poethko-Müller 2014). Indeed, discussions since the 1970's have acknowledged the need for specialised training for teaching during illness. Still, to date no curricular or state-recognised training or further education exists in the German-speaking countries. This lack of formalisation has led to unclear responsibilities (political, financial, scientific, and pedagogical) and an absence of systematic evaluation of pedagogical action in this field (Blanc 2014). Moreover, there is a persistent lack of interconnection between practical expertise and scientific knowledge (Castello and Pülschen 2018), which is problematic because students especially need timely and appropriate educational support in stressful situations such as illness. The illness-specific educational support requirements thus lead to special demands on teachers. To foster professional competence within a system, the COACTIV model provides a robust structural framework (Baumert and Mareike 2011). Professionalisation is understood as the interaction of four interrelated domains,

which can be adapted for research in Pb-KuS (Elbracht et al. 2025). In line with the needs assessment and the study's aim to identify key components of competence development in Pb-KuS, the investigated dimensions are based on this model. Specifically, the study focuses on professional knowledge and motivational dispositions as core elements of professional competence. Professional knowledge includes subject-matter, pedagogical-content, pedagogical-psychological, and organisational knowledge, while the motivational dimension encompasses intrinsic motivation and self-efficacy beliefs.

The legal framework for hospital schooling is grounded in international and national regulations. Internationally, the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (United Nations 2006) and the UN Convention on the rights of Children (Convention on the Rights of the Child 1989) ensure equal and non-discriminatory access to education, regardless of health status. In Switzerland, the Conference of Cantonal Ministers of Education (EDK) delegates responsibilities to cantons. In Germany, the Standing Conference of the Ministers of Education (Bildungsminister Konferenz 2025) defines education for long-term ill students in different settings under the supervision of local school authorities. In Austria, regulations are being described by the Federal Ministry of Education (BMB 2017) formally recognises hospital schools, ensuring educational continuity during illness.

Internationally, established concepts and training structures for hospital school educators already exist. In the United States and China, specialised programmes have been developed that provide teachers with both pedagogical and basic medical knowledge. These approaches reflect the understanding that hospital school educators must possess didactic and pedagogical skills and have a fundamental understanding of medical conditions, treatment processes, and psychosocial aspects (Lightfoot, Wright, and Sloper 1999; Mukherjee, Lightfoot, and Sloper 2000). In contrast, hospital school pedagogy remains marginal in teacher education in German-speaking countries. Experiences from Taiwan (Chen et al. 2015) reveal similar challenges: Even in a highly efficient healthcare system, hospital-based education is often informal, fragmented, and insufficiently institutionalised. The study calls for policy-level advocacy and professional training to ensure equitable access to education for children with chronic illnesses. Training is often informal or occurs only on the job, leading to significant disparities in professionalisation and a lack of systematic networking between universities and hospital schools (Kremsner et al. 2023; Langnickel et al. 2024). The absence of standardised training means that teachers must rely on individual experiences and collegial networks to navigate the diverse challenges of their practice. Despite decades of international recognition, the systematic professionalisation of hospital school educators remains severely underdeveloped, particularly in German-speaking contexts.

Taken together, these insights highlight a shared pattern across different healthcare and educational systems: Despite the known benefits of hospital schooling for children with chronic conditions, systemic implementation often remains inconsistent, underfunded, or insufficiently professionalised. Bridging this gap requires not only national policy initiatives, but also robust cross-sector collaboration and formalised teacher training programmes that address the medical-pedagogical interface.

This study aims to bridge the existing research gap by conducting a systematic needs assessment and developing concrete recommendations for establishing specialised

teacher education in Germany, Austria, and Switzerland. Using an online-based questionnaire, the study addresses two central research questions:

- (A) How do hospital school teachers evaluate the existing procedures and processes in their daily professional practice?
- (B) What are the needs identified by teachers in hospital schools?

The investigation considers both the existing challenges and the opportunities for structured professional development in this field. The findings provide a scientifically grounded basis for curriculum development and the implementation of a sustainable approach to professionalisation.

Materials and methods

Procedure

The present study was part of a trinational research project Pb-KuS funded by Movetia. The study was conducted in Germany, Switzerland, and Austria with the aim of developing a curriculum for teachers in hospital schools. The research team contacted representatives of the field of hospital schools, such as school principals and clinic managers, and asked them to select professionals to participate in the study. The professionals had to be involved in educational activities in hospital schools and/or in a home school and/or in a resuming school (i.e. the school to which a student returns). Data were collected over six weeks in February and March 2024 using an online questionnaire. School principals and clinic managers distributed the questionnaire link to the professionals. Participation was voluntary and unpaid.

Sample/participants

The sample consisted of 230 participants (73.5% female). The majority of respondents identified as classroom teachers (38.3%), subject teachers (17.4%), or school principals (20.9%), with an additional 21.6% working in multiple roles. Participants were primarily from Germany (66.5%), Switzerland (13.9%), and Austria (16.1%). Most (71.7%) were working in formally independent schools under the usual school administration hierarchy, whereas 13% were working in hospital schools formally attached to a clinic (with the head physician as supervisor). The majority of the sample worked exclusively in psychiatric clinics or departments (53.9%) or in somatic illness settings (21.7%), followed by a small percentage working in a student's original school or a receiving school (about 3% each). A notable proportion (16.8%) worked across more than one type of setting. Over half of the participants (50.9%) reported working with children encompassing psychological, somatic, and psychosomatic illnesses; 30.9% worked only with children with psychological illnesses, 12.6% with solely somatic illnesses, and 2.2% exclusively with psychosomatic illnesses. In terms of teaching levels, only 2.2% solely taught at the primary level, 2.6% in special education, and 6.1% at the secondary level, while the majority

(64.9%) taught across multiple school levels. Most participants were experienced professionals: 82.6% had more than two years of experience in their current institution. Regarding formal qualifications, 2.6% held a doctorate, 53.5% had a second state examination in teaching (a standard terminal qualification for teachers in Germany), 30.4% held a Master's degree, 10.0% a Bachelor's degree, and 17.8% reported other qualifications (including therapeutic or nursing qualifications such as physiotherapy or kinesiology certification).

Instruments

The online questionnaire included both closed and open-ended items covering several domains. It gathered information on participants' professional biography and everyday working life (e.g. current role, setting, tasks, and experiences), their perceptions of existing school processes and curricula, and their self-reported expertise and professional development. For example, participants were asked to list all their tasks/responsibilities in the hospital school, what they enjoy about their work, and what they find challenging in their work. They were also asked whether a specific curriculum for hospital schooling exists at their institution and to rate their satisfaction with certain aspects of their work (such as teaching across different school levels and managing transitions between hospital school and mainstream education). In addition, the survey included questions evaluating existing pre-service training and in-service training or continuing education opportunities for hospital school teaching, using 7-point Likert scales (1 = very insufficient to 7 = excellent). Participants were asked if they had ever attended any training related to pedagogy for illness and to rate the adequacy of current training offerings. Open-ended questions invited respondents to elaborate on their needs and suggestions for further training, specific knowledge they deem necessary for the job, and any other support they would find beneficial (such as supervision or networking). The questionnaire was reviewed by experts from the field before distribution to ensure content validity and clarity (social validation).

Data analysis

Quantitative data from closed questions were analysed using descriptive statistics (means, standard deviations, and frequency distributions) with SPSS 29. Likert-scale items are reported with mean (M) and standard deviation (SD). Qualitative data from open-ended questions were analysed using inductive content analysis, following Mayring's (2015) established qualitative content analysis approach, widely used in German-speaking educational research contexts. Two researchers independently coded the qualitative responses, iteratively developing a category system. Initial categories were derived inductively from a subset of responses (approximately 25% of the data), and the category system was then refined and applied to the full dataset. During this process, new categories were added as needed and others were merged or adjusted (forming a final catalogue of categories capturing the main themes in participants' answers). Regular team discussions were held to achieve consensus on the coding, and discrepancies were resolved through reflection on the meaning of responses. Cohen's κ ranged from .75 to .87, with a total of .81. This qualitative analysis allowed for the extraction of key themes and 'big points' raised by participants, which complement the quantitative findings. [Table 1](#) provides an overview of

Table 1. Overview of inductively derived main categories from the qualitative content analysis, including Cohen's κ values and number of coded segments per subcategory.

Category Subcategory	Cohen's Kappa	Number of ratings
Everyday working life		
Beneficial aspects	.76	592
Hindering aspects	.80	287
Professional enrichment and challenges.		
Enrichment	.75	336
Challenges	.75	282
Professional competences		
Personal skills	.87	452
Didactic skills	.83	206
Pedagogical-psychological skills	.81	283
Identified needs		
Specific needs and support	.80	363
Specific topics for additional training or further education/training	.75	91
Structure of additional and/or further training	.81	155
Subject-specific didactic content	.83	29
Content beyond specialised didactic	.78	75
Suggested teaching and learning methods	.79	195
Total	.81	3346

the main inductively derived categories from the qualitative content analysis, including Cohen's Kappa values and number of coded segments per subcategory.

Results

Professional background and current practices

The current landscape of hospital schooling in Germany, Austria, and Switzerland is characterised by a largely experienced and highly committed group of teachers working in diverse roles and settings. Almost all participants reported that they regularly collaborate with various professionals in their daily work, reflecting a high degree of interdisciplinarity. For example, teachers indicated that they maintain contact with medical staff (doctors, nurses, therapists), parents, school administrators of the students' home schools, and other specialists to provide holistic support to the student. Many respondents listed a wide range of responsibilities – from delivering individualised instruction across multiple subjects and grade levels, to coordinating with healthcare professionals, to managing students' transition back to their original schools.

When asked what they appreciate about working at a hospital school, teachers most frequently mentioned the variety and meaningfulness of their work. They highlighted varied tasks and the creative freedom in lesson design as positive aspects. The ability to work individually with children and adolescents and to tailor education to each student's needs was seen as a major advantage of this setting. Furthermore, many respondents valued the close multi-professional collaboration, noting that working with different professions (e.g. healthcare providers, social workers) enriched their practice and allowed them to support students more comprehensively. However, some challenges were reported. A few teachers pointed out structural or administrative difficulties, such as unclear responsibilities or a lack of resources and time, which can hinder their work. However, overall job satisfaction in this field appears to be high.

Indeed, a striking finding is that an overwhelming majority of respondents consider their position to be their dream job. Specifically, 86.7% of the teachers (among those who responded to this item, $n = 117$) reported that working at a hospital school is their dream job. Despite the inherent challenges, this suggests a strong vocational commitment and positive identification with their role. Furthermore, teachers also reported being satisfied with teaching across different school types and age groups. They were asked to rate their satisfaction with instructing students from various school levels (since in hospital schools one teacher may teach primary through secondary content). The mean satisfaction was high (5.5 on a 7-point scale, indicating between 'somewhat satisfied' and 'very satisfied'), reflecting that most teachers do not view the heterogeneity in student academic levels as a burden. This finding is noteworthy given that heterogeneity in mainstream classrooms is often cited as a stress factor for teachers. It appears that hospital school teachers, perhaps due to specialised mindset or smaller class groups, manage diversity of academic needs well and even embrace it as part of their job.

Another important aspect of teachers' daily work is managing students' transitions between their home schools and the hospital school. Respondents were asked to evaluate the procedures for transitioning students from the mainstream school to the hospital school and back to the mainstream school after recovery. The overall assessment of these transition processes was positive. On a 7-point scale (1 = very unsatisfied, 7 = very satisfied), the average ratings for transition management were above the neutral midpoint. Teachers rated the transition from the home school into the hospital school at $M = 5.2$ ($SD = 1.5$) and the transition from the hospital school back to mainstream education at $M = 5.0$ ($SD = 1.6$). In practical terms, many teachers reported well-established communication channels with the home schools and a general satisfaction with maintaining students' educational continuity. Qualitative comments reinforced this: teachers mentioned that flexible curricula and good cooperation between institutions help ensure that students re-enter their regular classes as smoothly as possible. Nevertheless, a few challenges were noted, such as occasional gaps in communication or differences in expectations between hospital school teachers and mainstream teachers. Despite these, the majority of participants described the transition processes as functioning rather well, indicating a generally effective transition management in current practice.

Evaluation of training and identified needs

A central goal of this study was to assess existing training and education programmes for hospital school teachers and to identify the needs perceived by practitioners in this field. The results reveal a clear message: teachers feel that current training opportunities are inadequate and strongly desire more specialised preparation and support. Most teachers in our sample (72.6%) had at some point participated in a training or further education programme related to teaching in the context of illness. Despite this, their ratings of both initial teacher education and continuing training specific to hospital schooling were very low. On a 7-point scale ranging from 1 (insufficient) to 7 (excellent), respondents on average rated the current initial training offerings at $M = 2.09$ ($SD = 1.30$) and the continuing education offerings at $M = 2.95$ ($SD = 1.67$). These means are close to the 'insufficient/poor' end of the scale, highlighting that teachers perceive a significant gap in formal preparation for the demands of their job. In open-ended comments, many teachers noted that they primarily learned how to teach ill students

Table 2. Summary of the most frequently mentioned needs and support requests expressed by participants in the open-ended responses.

Subcategory	Memo	Number of ratings
Specific needs and support		
Training and professional development	Participants wish for more training and professional development.	112
Medical Knowledge	Participants state medical knowledge as a specific need to work in the field of clinic schools	101
Supervision and Coaching	Participants state more supervision and coaching opportunities as needed	48
Networking and exchange with peers	Participants state a need of more networking and exchange with their peers as needed	36
(...)	(...)	(...)

through practice or through informal peer exchange, rather than through structured programmes. When asked what improvements they would like to see in training and professional development, 112 teachers provided concrete suggestions. Table 2 summarises the most frequently mentioned needs and support wishes expressed by participants in the open-ended responses. The most frequently mentioned need – by far – was for a broader range of training content in medical knowledge.

Teachers feel they require more medical background knowledge to teach and support students with various health conditions effectively. This was echoed in multiple parts of the survey: for instance, in a separate question about necessary knowledge for working in hospital schools, 101 respondents (almost half the sample) explicitly highlighted medical knowledge (such as understanding illnesses, treatments, and their implications for learning) as essential. Beyond medical topics, teachers also called for more training in pedagogy tailored to students experiencing illness (mentioned by 9 respondents) and in communication skills (mentioned by 7 respondents) – for example, skills for communicating with healthcare professionals, with parents, or with students who may be anxious or in pain. Additionally, some participants pointed to the need for knowledge about legal and organisational aspects of hospital schooling (e.g. rights of students, coordination with health services), though this was a less frequent theme than medical and pedagogical content.

Beyond subject-matter knowledge, the survey uncovered a strong demand for professional support and networking opportunities. Many teachers expressed that working in a hospital school can at times be isolating, as there are usually only a small number of colleagues who share this specialised role. Nearly 21% of respondents (48 teachers) indicated a need for regular supervision or coaching to reflect on challenging cases and their own emotional well-being. Likewise, 36 teachers (about 16%) emphasised the importance of opportunities for networking and exchange with peers – for instance, through regional or international meetings, conferences, or online platforms where hospital school educators can share experiences and resources. Such networking could help disseminate best practices and reduce the feeling of constantly having to reinvent solutions at each hospital school.

Teachers provided insightful suggestions when considering what form additional training or further education should take. A modular training structure was favoured: respondents envisioned a programme composed of modules that could be completed flexibly, possibly accumulating to a certification. This modular approach could allow differentiation for teachers

who come from various backgrounds (special education, general education, etc.) and need to focus on different areas. Teachers also called for interactive and practical learning formats rather than purely lecture-based instruction. They suggested that programmes integrate theoretical knowledge with case-based learning and hands-on components. For instance, role-plays, workshops on real-life scenarios, and internships or observations in medical settings were proposed to bridge theory and practice (29 respondents explicitly mentioned the importance of combining theory with practice). As one teacher noted, practical training with case examples would be highly valuable. In terms of content, apart from medical basics, participants underscored individualisation and differentiation strategies as crucial – i.e. how to adapt teaching to their students' diverse academic and health needs. They also pointed to the need for learning about extended educational opportunities, such as using digital tools or alternative instructional methods for students who cannot attend school regularly, and methods for managing student learning in the context of illness, which includes addressing issues like fatigue, irregular attendance, or cognitive impairments due to treatments. Finally, regarding the training delivery mode, respondents would appreciate digital formats – for example, online courses or webinars – since hospital school teachers are spread across different regions and often cannot easily travel for prolonged courses. However, they noted that digital training should still be interactive and include practical tasks or exercises in order to be effective.

In summary, the results clearly demonstrate that while hospital school teachers are passionate and adaptable professionals, they currently operate in a context of limited formal preparation. They proactively identify key areas – notably medical knowledge, specialised pedagogy, and communication – where enhanced training is needed, and they advocate for structural supports like supervision and professional networks. These findings provide concrete targets for developing a specialised curriculum and support system for teachers in this field.

Discussion

In the following section, we discuss our results to address our research questions. Based on the theoretical framework, we collected data across multiple dimensions of professional competence. The findings on specific knowledge components provide insights into essential subject-matter, pedagogical, psychological, and organisational competences that professionals in our sample consider necessary for successful work in the field of Pb-KuS. In addition, motivational dimensions were examined, and the results offer information on the satisfaction levels within our sample.

Research question A: current state of hospital schooling (Pb-ku)

The first research question focused on how hospital school teachers rate the existing procedures and processes in their daily work life. The study findings indicate that teachers generally view their daily work processes positively, despite the complex challenges of the environment. The majority of participants reported high satisfaction with their teaching role and the inclusive educational practices they employ. Notably, hospital school teachers do not perceive the extreme heterogeneity of their student population (in terms of ages, grade levels, and medical conditions) as a burden in the way that many mainstream teachers view

heterogeneity in inclusive classrooms. On the contrary, these teachers value the diversity and see it as an integral part of their dream job. They have adapted to teaching students across a range of academic levels and health needs, often in one-on-one or very small group settings, which likely contributes to their ability to individualise learning effectively. Furthermore, teachers reported that key procedures in their work context are functioning well, such as interdisciplinary collaboration and student transition processes. Most teachers regularly collaborate with medical staff and other professionals, suggesting that multi-professional teamwork is well established as a daily practice. This teamwork is essential for addressing the holistic needs of chronically ill students and is evidently embraced by teachers. Additionally, the process of managing transitions between a student's mainstream school and the hospital school is generally rated as satisfactory to good. Teachers gave above-average ratings for both the transition into hospital school and the return to mainstream school, suggesting that communication and coordination with regular schools are often well-established in practice. However, it is essential to note that a significant gap in current practice is the lack of formal curricula designed explicitly for hospital schooling: 84% of teachers said that no special curriculum exists at their institution. In practice, this means teachers must often improvise or adapt the mainstream curricula to fit the hospital context, relying on their personal expertise. In summary, the current state of Pb-KuS is characterised by highly motivated educators who have developed workable solutions and informal processes to ensure students' education continues during illness, albeit without the benefit of standardised structures or curricula.

Research question B: needs of hospital school teachers

Our second research question examined what needs teachers in hospital schools identify and how relevant these needs are. The study revealed several critical needs, unanimously identified by teachers, that are highly relevant for their professional development and the advancement of the field. First and foremost is the need for enhanced content knowledge and skills training, especially in medical and psychosocial domains. Teachers feel insufficiently prepared in understanding specific illnesses and their implications for learning, which they consider fundamental knowledge for their role. The call for more medical knowledge was the most frequent request and thus is of paramount relevance. Equally important is the need for strategies and pedagogical methods tailored to students with health issues – respondents want to learn best practices for instructing students who may have intermittent attendance, cognitive impairments due to treatment, or emotional distress. Communication skills training (for interacting with families and healthcare providers) was another notable need. Regarding support structures, teachers expressed an acute need for professional support such as supervision, indicating that the emotional burden of their work (witnessing severe illness or juggling educational decisions in life-threatening contexts) can be heavy and that they would benefit from regular reflective supervision or coaching. The need for networking and exchange opportunities is also highly relevant: given that hospital school teachers are few and often geographically dispersed, creating platforms for peer-to-peer learning and support is crucial. These identified needs are not abstract or secondary – they are directly drawn from the teachers' own experiences and were repeatedly emphasised, underlining their relevance. The fact that teachers themselves converge on similar priorities (medical knowledge, specialised pedagogy, communication,

supervision, networking) provides a clear roadmap for what any future curriculum or programme must address. Notably, teachers also have specific ideas on how these needs should be met, advocating for modular, practice-oriented training delivered in accessible formats. This suggests that they have thought deeply about their professional gaps and are eager for concrete, actionable improvements. In conclusion, the identified needs are highly relevant in that they point to the essential competencies and support mechanisms that teachers currently lack but deem necessary to perform their jobs effectively and sustainably.

Content implications for curriculum development

The findings carry significant implications for the content and design of a specialised curriculum for Pb-KuS. Firstly, any such curriculum must integrate interdisciplinary content, especially foundational medical knowledge, into teacher training. Unlike general teacher education, which focuses primarily on pedagogy and subject matter, a curriculum for hospital school educators should include modules on paediatric diseases, treatment protocols, and their educational implications. This could involve collaboration with healthcare professionals in delivering parts of the training. For example, physicians or nurses could teach educators about chronic conditions like diabetes, epilepsy, or the side effects of chemotherapy that might affect a student's ability to concentrate or attend school. The emphasis on medical knowledge in our study mirrors the practice in some international contexts where hospital teachers receive training in medical aspects (Mukherjee, Lightfoot, and Sloper 2000). Incorporating this content would directly respond to the teachers' call for more competence in this area. Secondly, the curriculum should reinforce inclusive pedagogical strategies and differentiation techniques tailored to the hospital context. The heterogeneity in hospital schools requires teachers to be adept at individualised instruction, scaffolding learning for students who might be at very different levels or who might need to work in short, intensive bursts when their health permits. The content should cover strategies for maintaining continuity of instruction (e.g. coordinating with the home school's syllabus, using e-learning for students who are convalescing at home) and adapting assessment methods for students who cannot follow the standard timeline. In essence, the curriculum needs to prepare teachers for a unique form of adaptive expertise: being flexible and responsive to each student's health situation while still promoting academic progress. Thirdly, strong emphasis should be placed on communication and counselling skills. As hospital school teachers often function as liaisons between the medical world and the education system, they must communicate effectively with doctors (to understand medical recommendations), with parents (to provide guidance and reassurance regarding the child's education), and with students (who may be coping with anxiety, trauma, or altered self-esteem due to illness). Training in empathetic communication, conflict resolution, and inter-professional dialogue is therefore a vital content implication.

Finally, the results highlight that teaching in a hospital school is as much about emotional labour and psychological support as it is about academic instruction. Therefore, the curriculum should include content on psychosocial support, perhaps drawing from school psychology or counselling. Teachers might benefit from learning basics of trauma-informed education or strategies to support students' mental health and resilience. In sum, the content

implications point to a rich, multidisciplinary curriculum that blends pedagogy, special education, medicine, and psychology – a blend necessary to equip teachers for the complexities of hospital schooling adequately.

Methodological limitations

While this study provides valuable insights, several methodological limitations must be considered. First, the length and comprehensiveness of the online questionnaire may have led to respondent fatigue. The survey was quite extensive, covering many topics, and this is reflected in the fact that not all participants answered every question (for example, only 117 of 230 responded to the dream job item towards the end). It is possible that those who did answer the later questions (such as open-ended needs) were particularly motivated, which might bias the results towards the opinions of more engaged individuals. Second, the sampling strategy – relying on school principals and clinic managers to nominate participants – may have introduced a selection bias. The sample might overrepresent teachers who are more involved or enthusiastic (since they were likely the ones put forward to participate) and underrepresent those who are more isolated or less engaged. It also primarily reached teachers currently employed in hospital schools or similar roles; thus, our results do not include the perspectives of those who may have left the field, possibly due to unmet needs or burnout. Third, as a self-report study, there is the limitation of social desirability bias. Teachers who take pride in their work might have painted a somewhat optimistic picture of their coping and success (e.g. in handling heterogeneity or transitions), potentially downplaying difficulties. Conversely, when highlighting needs, they might have been more candid. We attempted to mitigate this by ensuring anonymity and encouraging honest responses, but some bias cannot be ruled out. Additionally, since the study was conducted in three countries with different educational systems, there might be context-specific nuances that a single aggregated analysis could overlook. For instance, teachers in Switzerland have the opportunity to pursue an education program in hospital pedagogy, worth 15 ECTS. Since Austria is formally recognising hospital schooling as a distinct school type, they also provide a corresponding accredited study program. University students can complete a full post-graduate program comprising 60 ECTS. Lastly, the qualitative content analysis, while thorough, is interpretive. Although we followed systematic procedures (iterative coding and team consensus), other researchers might categorise responses differently. Future research could complement these findings with in-depth interviews or observations to validate and enrich the interpretation of the survey data. In summary, these limitations suggest caution in generalising the findings to all contexts and underscore the need for further studies, but they do not diminish the clear signals that emerge regarding teacher needs and satisfaction in this specialised field.

Practical implications for educational practice and policy

The results of this study have immediate practical implications for educational practice, teacher professional development, and policy in the realm of pedagogy for chronically ill students. For teacher education providers and universities, there is a clear mandate to develop and offer targeted programmes or courses for (aspiring)

hospital school teachers. This could take the form of a dedicated certificate or a module within special education training programmes. Teacher training colleges could collaborate internationally – perhaps leveraging the emerging international network of universities and hospital schools mentioned in our project description – to share curricula and resources, since the pool of experts in each country is small. Education ministries and school authorities in Germany, Austria, and Switzerland should recognise ‘Continuity in education for children and adolescents with medical challenges’ as a specialisation deserving of official recognition and funding. Educational authorities worldwide should consider adopting structured qualification programmes, informed by international best practices highlighted in this study. The lack of a state-recognised specialisation (as highlighted by Castello and Pülschen 2018) means there is currently no formal career path or incentive structure for teachers in this field. Policymakers could address this by creating official specialist roles or advanced training credits for hospital schooling, thereby professionalising the field. Practically, this could also alleviate workload issues: if recognised, schools might receive funding to hire additional staff or provide prep time for hospital teachers given their wide-ranging duties. The strong desire for multi-professional teamwork and better transition management implies that school administrations and hospitals should formalise collaboration channels. For example, establishing regular case conferences that include teachers, or assigning a liaison person in mainstream schools for each hospitalised student, can improve communication. Our findings that teachers view transitions positively suggests that some regions have good models in place; these models should be documented and possibly standardised across regions so that every hospital school and mainstream school knows the transition protocol (e.g. exchange of student portfolios, joint planning meetings before reintegration). The call for supervision and support has implications for employing institutions: school boards or hospital administrations should consider providing access to counselling or peer-supervision groups for their teachers. This could help sustain teacher well-being and prevent burnout, ensuring that the high job satisfaction (the dream job sentiment) endures in the long term. Additionally, practical guides or toolkits could be developed as immediate resources – for instance, a handbook on pedagogy for illness, or an online platform for resource sharing among hospital teachers (which could be initiated by a central education authority or a teacher association). For the broader educational community, these findings also serve as a reminder of the importance of inclusive education principles. Teachers in mainstream schools can learn from hospital school teachers about individualised instruction. They could potentially apply some of these methods in their own classrooms to better accommodate students with health issues who attend intermittently. Finally, an implication for practice is strengthening transition programmes such as reintegration tutoring or partial attendance plans. Given that hospital school teachers strive to keep students on track, mainstream schools should reciprocally plan how to integrate returning students (perhaps through gradual re-entry schedules or supplemental tutoring). In summary, the practical steps recommended include: developing specialised training programmes, formalising the hospital school teacher role through policy, providing emotional and professional support structures, and enhancing collaboration between educational and medical systems. Implementing these steps will directly address the ‘big points’ raised by teachers and

ultimately improve educational continuity and outcomes for students whose lives are disrupted by illness.

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Ethical statement

This study adhered to the ethical standards outlined in the guidelines of the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors (ICMJE) regarding research involving human participants. All participants were adult professionals working in hospital school settings in Germany, Austria, and Switzerland. Participation was voluntary, anonymous, and without any form of compensation. No sensitive personal data were collected, and the study did not involve any physical or psychological intervention or manipulation.

According to national regulations in all three countries and in line with the ICMJE standards for non-invasive survey research with minimal risk, this study was exempt from the requirement of formal ethics committee approval. Participants received all relevant information about the study's aims and procedures and gave their informed consent by voluntarily completing the online questionnaire.

Statement

During the preparation of this work, the authors used ChatGPT (version GPT-4-turbo, May 2025) to improve the readability and language of the manuscript under human oversight and control. After using this service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

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